
Latest performance results of the High-Angle TPC in the upgraded T2K off-axis near detector

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Recently published paper on HA-TPC performance!

The results presented in this talk are taken from:

ND280 Performance of the High-Angle Time Projection Chambers in the Upgraded T2K Off-Axis Near Detector

[Submitted on 23 Nov 2025]

<https://arxiv.org/abs/2511.18650>

1. Introduction to ND280 Upgrade

The T2K Experiment

T2K is a long baseline accelerator neutrino (anti-neutrino) experiment.

Far Detector

2.5° off-axis

Neutrino Beam

Near Detector Complex

MR (Main Ring): accelerates protons up to 30 GeV.

Neutrino Beamline: ν_μ or $\bar{\nu}_\mu$ with a peak at 0.6 GeV.

2.5° off-axis

ND280 constrains and corrects flux and cross section systematics.

Measure ν_μ or $\bar{\nu}_\mu$ disappearance and ν_e or $\bar{\nu}_e$ appearance to estimate neutrino oscillation parameters:

δ_{CP} , θ_{23} , Δm^2_{23} , θ_{13}

The ND280 Upgrade

After removing the P0D (π^0 – detector), three new type of detectors have been installed in the same volume:

- **Super Fine-Grained Detector active target**
- **2 High-Angle TPCs**
- **6 TOF scintillator panels**

The muon detection at high angles improves \rightarrow 4π coverage

<https://arxiv.org/pdf/2108.11779>

- \rightarrow Proton detection threshold is lowered to 300 MeV/c.
- \rightarrow Neutrons can be detected through time-of-flight in the SFGD.

The ND280 Upgrade

Super Fine-Grained Detector (SFGD): Active target detector made of 2 million scintillating cubes read by WLS fibers in three directions.

Time Of Flight (TOF): 6 panels of 20 scintillator bars each, read by SiPMs, cover entirely (4π) the volume of upgrade detectors.

High-Angle Time Projection Chambers (HA-TPCs)

Features :

- New field cage design to minimize dead space and maximize tracking volume.
- Replacement of standard bulk-MicroMegas with new resistive MicroMegas that improved spatial resolution using fewer pads.

Requirements:

1. Momentum resolution $\sigma_p/p < 10\%$ at 1 GeV/c: for neutrino energy estimation.
2. Energy resolution $\sigma(dE/dx) < 10\%$: to allow PID of electrons and muons
3. Spatial resolution $\sim 800\mu\text{m}$
4. Field cage made of lightweight and low budget material, less than $3\% X_0$

ERAM (Encapsulated Resistive Anode Micromegas) detector innovation:

- Charge is spread on a resistive layer, induced signal on more pads improves spatial resolution
- Protection from sparks

Working conditions:

T2K gas: Ar:CF₄:iC₄H₁₀ (95:3:2)
 Drift velocity: 7.8 cm/μs
 Drift length: 1 m
 Cathode voltage: -27.5 kV
 Electric field: 275 V/cm
 Dimensions: 2.0 × 0.8 × 1.8 m³
 E field uniformity < 10⁻³ at 15 mm from walls

2. Field cage and ERAMs characterization

Field cage strips layout

- Strip width 3 mm, pitch 5 mm
- 784 resistors of 5.1 M Ω forming two dividers (392 for each) connected in parallel providing a $R_{eq} = 1 \text{ G}\Omega$.

Electrical tests on the Field Cage

- Electrical tests were performed to validate the FC before resistor soldering.
- Very high insulation resistance (15 T Ω) across the wall (Mantle Resistance).

Load tests:

- weights up to 200 kg applied to the upper flanges.
- showed elastic behavior, with no permanent deformation.

Metrology:

- CAD model overall respected within 500 μm , locally 800 μm on cured areas.
- Wall parallelism is verified. No deviation greater than 0.93 mm was found.

Electric field

A study of selected cosmic tracks passing near the cathode revealed unexpected distortions of the electric field.

In the original design there is no gap between the cathode and the wall. The first strip starting next to the cathode.

Main differences from TDR:

- Cathode distance from the wall is 12 mm.
- The first strip starts 8 mm away from the cathode.

Simulating the electric field map, with COMSOL, with the updated geometry, the apparent curvature of the tracks is cured.

The application of Electric field map on reconstructed events reduces their apparent curvature (in absence of B field).

ERAM detectors characterization

A test bench was setup at CERN to test ERAM detectors performance before installation.

1. Mesh pulsing: to spot any electrical or geometric defects.

Comparing the average maximum amplitude and the standard deviation of each induced waveform we could detected possible issues.

Plots from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2023.168534>

Utmost important to understand detector response!

2. X-ray source from ⁵⁵Fe: scan of the pads to reconstruct the RC mapping and a gain mapping.

(a) RC map of ERAM-30.

(b) RC distribution of all the pads of ERAM-30.

(a) Gain map of ERAM-30

(b) Gain distribution of ERAM-30

ERAM detectors characterization

Summary of the performances of the different ERAM detectors produced for the HA-TPCs.

Different epochs in the production can be identified and are indicated by the red vertical dashed lines.

- 1 RC values:**
 - All detectors up to ERAM-37 exhibit similar RC values.
 - Final batch of DLC foils has higher surface resistivity.
- 2 Gain:** three distinct production periods are observed
 - **First:** mechanical defects visible on the gain values.
 - **Second:** improvements due to changed stiffener glueing procedure. We see reduced gain spread and decreased mean gain.
 - **Third:** the amplification gap is smaller due to a reduction in Pyralux thickness. The effect is an increasing of the mean gain.
- 3 Energy resolution:** values compatible with the target of 10%.

Candle plots

3. Simulation and reconstruction

1. The drift of electrons in the drift volume is described by the **Langevin** equation:

$$\vec{V}_d = \frac{\mu}{1 + (\omega\tau)^2} \left(\vec{E} + (\omega\tau) \frac{\vec{E} \times \vec{B}}{|\vec{B}|} + (\omega\tau)^2 \frac{(\vec{E} \cdot \vec{B})\vec{B}}{|\vec{B}|^2} \right)$$

$$\mu = \frac{e}{m} \tau \quad \omega = \frac{eB}{m}$$

2. In the gap between the ERAM anode mesh and the DLC, primary electrons generate avalanches, leading to signal amplification. This process is modeled using a **Polya** distribution:

$$P_m(g) = \frac{m^m}{\Gamma(m)} \frac{g^{m-1}}{G^m} \exp\left(-m \frac{g}{G}\right)$$

- G is the gain and comes from X-ray tests
- m is tuned to match the 9% resolution

3. The charge spreading on the DLC is simulated using a 2D diffusion equation depending on the RC parameter:

$$\rho(r, t) = \frac{RC}{4\pi t} \exp\left(-\frac{r^2 RC}{4t}\right)$$

The total charge on a pad is calculated by integrating the density over the area of a pad.

4. Convolution with the electronic response

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2023.168534> On the signal model

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2025.170803> On the electronic noise

- 1) **Waveforms conversion to ‘hits’**: identify the maximum of each waveform (the charge) and the hit’s time.
- 2) **A pattern recognition algorithm** is used to identify track segments and merge them across multiple ERAMs.
- 3) **Hits are then grouped in clusters**, and each cluster orientation is chosen **depending on the local track direction (horizontal, vertical, diagonal)**.

4) **Position Determination:** Precise position found using **Logarithmic Charge Ratios** $\ln(Q_1/Q_0)$ and $\ln(Q_2/Q_1)$ from the leading pad, exploiting charge sharing.

5) **Parametrization:** Ratios converted to continuous position offset (dz) via iterative polynomial fit:

$$f(z) = \alpha(\ln(Q))^3 + \beta \ln(Q)$$

Correlation plots

1

$$dz = \alpha_{10} \ln^3 \left(\frac{Q_1}{Q_0} \right) + \beta_{10} \ln \left(\frac{Q_1}{Q_0} \right)$$

2

$$dz = \alpha_{21} \ln^3 \left(\frac{Q_2}{Q_1} \right) + \beta_{21} \ln \left(\frac{Q_2}{Q_1} \right)$$

4. HATPC performance results

Spatial resolution

After the fitting the tracks, the **residual for each cluster** is computed as:

$$\text{residual} = \sqrt{(y^{\text{rec}} - y^{\text{fit}})^2 + (z^{\text{rec}} - z^{\text{fit}})^2} - R$$

The distribution of residuals is fitted with a **double Gaussian**, and the spatial resolution is computed from the standard deviation of the narrower one.

Beam data

Cosmic data

Beam and cosmic data combined

The spatial resolution better than 600 μm over the full drift range in both data and simulations.

Momentum resolution

Momentum resolution is defined as: $\frac{p_{rec} - p_{true}}{p_{true}}$

The results are in agreement with the Gluckstern formula predictions: $\frac{\sigma_{p_t}}{p_t} = \sigma_{xy} [\text{m}] \frac{p_t [\text{GeV}/c]}{e B [\text{T}] l^2 [\text{m}^2]} \sqrt{\frac{720}{N_p + 4}}$

- Linear trend is ok because of $\frac{\sigma_{p_t}}{p_t} \propto p_t$
- Horizontal tracks resolution is better because they are usually longer, and $\frac{\sigma_{p_t}}{p_t} \propto \frac{1}{l^2}$

Negative charged particles

Positive charged particles

Both $\frac{dE}{dx}$ and its resolution are fundamental to do PID in a TPC.

The energy loss is estimated assuming a continuous linear charge density along the track.

- After dividing data in momentum bins, we fill a histogram with corresponding $\frac{dE}{dx}$ values.
- From the Gaussian fit, the mean energy loss (μ) and the standard deviation (σ) are extracted, from which the energy resolution is computed.
- Data and Monte Carlo are in agreement.

$$\frac{\sigma}{\mu} \sim 5\%$$

Energy loss resolution

Summary plots of **energy loss resolution in function of:**

- **Momentum, for horizontal tracks** (beam)
- **Momentum, for vertical tracks** (cosmics)
- **Number of clusters**

Plots show good agreement between data and Monte Carlo.

Matched requirement: energy loss resolution < 10%

In the short term, **two campaigns will be conducted at CERN: a laser test and a beam test.**

We are interested in two main studies that can be performed with a well know source, instead of cosmics:

- **Investigation of the electric field map**
- **Evaluation of the spatial resolution performance**

Laser test

- We are preparing a spare half-volume TPC instrumented with 7 complete ERAM detectors and a quartz window as laser entrance.
- 266 nm Nd:YAG Q-switching laser.
- A movable mirror is installed to direct the laser beam in all directions.

Quartz window

Test beam

Scheduled for April-May 2026 at the T10 line of the PS accelerator

Photo from test beam at CERN PS in 2022

Movable mirror

- The ND280 detector successfully installed two large HA-TPCs as part of the upgrade, featuring innovative resistive Micromegas technology and a field cage composed of thin composite walls.
- The final HA-TPC design comes from prototyping, construction, validation and characterization of components which started in 2018.
- **Field cage performance:**
 - Electrical and mechanical test validated the field cage wall structure.
 - Electric field non-uniformities come from the 8mm distance between the cathode and the first strip introduced by the revision of the cathode design.
 - A 3D electric field model has been validated to characterize the distortions.
- **ERAM performance:** production results, including gain and RC measurements and their correlation with production parameters, were presented.
- **HA-TPC performance:**
 - **Requirements are matched for spatial resolution $O(800\mu\text{m})$ and dE/dx resolution $<10\%$, for all track lengths and inclination.**
 - Monte Carlo and data are in good agreement.

HA-TPCs are foreseen to operate as part of the Hyper-K long-baseline physics program!

Thank you for your attention!

